

GUIDEBOOK

The CARE Principles and data ethics:

A practical guide for SSH researchers in The Netherlands

Part of the project

'Beyond Personal Data: RDNL training on hard-to-share data for SSH early-career researchers'

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Licence

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Working definitions

In the guidebook we understand these core concepts in the following way:

Indigenous community: We refer to the United Nations (UN) [67] definition of Indigenous peoples and refer to “Indigenous peoples” and “Indigenous communities” as equivalent. The UN defines Indigenous peoples as “peoples in independent countries who are regarded as indigenous on account of their descent from the populations [which] inhabited the country, or a geographical region to which the country belongs, at the time of conquest or colonisation or the establishment of present state boundaries and who, irrespective of their legal status, retain some or all of their own social, economic, cultural and political institutions”. Recognition of Indigenous communities throughout the world is still on a spectrum. While some communities are recognised as sovereign nations and have internal governance in place to manage all affairs of the Indigenous community/nation in relation to third parties, other communities may be not formally recognised or even opposed by the government of the state they are located in.

The CARE Principles (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) are a framework for the governance of data collected in and by Indigenous communities worldwide that serve the needs of Indigenous peoples in relation to the preservation of their tangible and intangible heritage as well as the foregrounding

and advancement of their community interests and wellbeing. These are specific and determined by each self-organised community or group of Indigenous communities.

The FAIR Principles describe properties of data and metadata to make them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. The FAIR Principles are widely recognised as valuable for the quality and reusability of data across scientific domains and are often referred to in the Research Data Management Policies of key funders and Research Performing Organisations worldwide.

Data governance refers to the organisational structure, oversight and processes involved in the management of data. Data governance has a technical aspect, in that the infrastructure used needs to allow for governance decisions to be implemented as intended in relation to, e.g., the storage, permissions and access levels, provenance tracking, data sharing, etc. In addition, data governance relates to the legal agreements and roles and responsibilities attached to the data throughout its lifecycle.

CARE-informed data governance consists of frameworks and practices that are inspired by the CARE Principles but are not directly developed or related to self-identified Indigenous communities or

peoples. Elements of CARE such as deriving community benefit from research data, co-developing governance agreements with a research community in light of risks or benefits they see; striving to structure and label data in line with the community language, culture and ways of knowing; and considering how the data itself contributes to addressing current or historical injustices faced by the community can be applicable to other groups as well, e.g., patient organisations, refugee groups, environmental groups, LGBTQ+ groups.

Data sovereignty refers to the level of control that organisations or communities can wield over how and when their data is used. The International Data Spaces Association [68] suggests that data sovereignty is a spectrum and it is about finding the right balance between keeping data safe and sharing it to gain added value.

Free, Prior and Informed Consent [69] is a process mandated by the United Nations Convention for the Rights of Indigenous peoples that requires states and agencies to collaborate with Indigenous communities to obtain Free, Prior, and Informed Consent (FPIC) for legal and administrative measures that affect them. This means that consent is given without intimidation or manipulation, that communities have adequate time to exhaust their decision-making processes and structures to come to a decision, and that all relevant information is shared with communities in an appropriate manner for the decisions to be taken.

Introduction

About the project

Sharing research data as openly as possible is key to responsible and reusable research: it increases the transparency of research and increases the chances that data will contribute to future studies. One of the main bottlenecks to sharing research data in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) is that many datasets contain personal data, which legally and ethically cannot be shared openly. Consequently, attention has been mostly focused on the challenges posed by these sorts of datasets. While protecting personal data from unwanted disclosure is

a crucial issue, there are many other reasons why data can be hard to share that have not yet been sufficiently addressed.

In response to this, a short project entitled 'Beyond personal data: RDNL training on hard-to-share data for SSH early-career researchers' was initiated by project partners DANS, SURF, Erasmus University Rotterdam (International Institute of Social Studies as well as ODISSEI), Leiden University, and the Promovendi Network Nederland (PNN), and funded through the Dutch Research Council (NWO)

via the Thematic Digital Competence Centre Social Sciences & Humanities (TDCC-SSH). The project ran for 12 months during 2025, and this guide is one of the outcomes.

As the scope of non-personal hard-to-share data is wide, we identified three specific bottlenecks to address during the project, chosen based on current gaps in training and guidance, as well as what could be feasibly addressed in this project:

- Hard to share data in the Social Sciences and Humanities
- Sharing field notes
- The CARE Principles and data ethics

For each of these topics, a half-day in-person training workshop was organised, of which the training materials have been published (see Section 'Additional Resources'). In order to extend this work of helping researchers to navigate this complex topic, we also proposed to write a guide on each topic. You are currently reading the third guide.

About this guide: The CARE Principles and Data Ethics

The relationship between research ethics, data ethics, and data governance that serves the needs of different types of communities is explored in depth by various actors spanning cross-cutting scientific and community contexts. The CARE Principles

are one prominent result of such work. They offer a structured and close-to-practice framework for Indigenous data governance, and they can also provide inspiration for conversations on data governance for other vulnerable communities. For the latter, we use the term "CARE-informed".

However, in the context of Dutch universities and other Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), CARE and CARE-informed data governance has yet to materialise into clear, proximate guidance that can steer researchers in their daily choices of whether to share research data, with whom to share, and how to share, while remaining compliant with institutional policies and practices¹.

With this guide, we hope to try and bridge this gap, and support early-career researchers who wish to actively reflect on how to apply CARE and CARE-informed practices in their research while acknowledging the role that RPOs, funders, heritage organisations, and other institutions would need to play in their facilitation.

The guide is divided in two parts. In the first part we introduce the CARE Principles, their relevance for Indigenous data governance and how they could be applicable for other vulnerable communities. In addition, we highlight some choices that Dutch RPOs can make in terms of data management and ethics review practices to support adoption of CARE. In the second

1 A recent positive step that we were made aware of just before the publication of this guide is the inclusion of the CARE principles in the [Strategy of the VU Network Research Data Support Roadmap 2026 - 2030](#).

part we introduce guiding questions for early-career researchers related to each CARE principle, supplemented by examples and best practices in the reference list. These guiding questions emerged from two workshops we held on this topic: a workshop with early-career researchers at the International Institute of Social Studies in The Hague in May 2025 (see Section 'Additional Resources' below for the workshop slides) and a workshop at the Open Science Festival 2025.

As our workshop participants acknowledged, the developing state of awareness and institutional and infrastructure readiness in The Netherlands does not allow us to provide ready-made solutions. Our aim is that this guide becomes a trusted reference for the conversations that we hope will take place.

Positionality Statements

Bora Lushaj

I do not myself have Indigenous heritage. I was born in Tirana, Albania and was educated in Tirana, Oxford, Nijmegen, and Leiden. I have a background in linguistics and have spent a few years researching the formal aspects of rhythmic changes during prolonged language contact between Italo-Albanian (Arbëresh dialects) and Southern Italian dialects.

I have lived in the Netherlands for the past 16 years and currently work as a Research Data Steward for the Erasmus School of Law, the International Institute of Social Studies, as well as the Engagement and Research Services, part of Erasmus University

Rotterdam. My perspective on research, the role of researchers and research institutions, and the duties of care for research data have been influenced by my cultural and professional embeddings.

Jing-Yi Magraw

It is important to highlight that I myself do not have Indigenous heritage. I'm biracial (Chinese and English) but I was educated in the UK and the Netherlands, which means that my perspective on research has inevitably been shaped by this. My academic background has been in religious studies, with a focus on religion and law, and I currently work in the research ethics team at Erasmus University Rotterdam.

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The CARE Principles

The CARE Principles (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) are a framework for the governance of data collected in and by Indigenous communities worldwide [1]. They are applicable to both scientific data [2], [3], [4] and data collected primarily for non-scientific purposes, e.g., data of Indigenous peoples collected on behalf of different authorities for the purposes of policy making. Each principle is broken down into three sub-principles to guide reflection and implementation as you can see on the image above [6].

Collective Benefit asks that research data is designed and reused in ways that allow Indigenous communities to derive benefit from it. At a high level, it encourages governments and institutions to facilitate collective benefit by promoting Indigenous innovation and self-directed development, as made explicit in *C1: For inclusive development and innovation*. *C2: For improved governance and citizen engagement* acknowledges the importance of data in driving both internal and external policies [5] affecting Indigenous peoples, by increasing transparency and understanding of Indigenous peoples, territories and resources. *C3: For equitable outcomes* advocates that heritage and knowledge embedded in Indigenous data, based on Indigenous values should provide value and positive outcomes for Indigenous communities.

Authority to Control asks that Indigenous communities are actively involved in the data

governance and stewardship through legal and technical means. *A1: Recognizing rights and interests*, encourages the recognition of individual and collective rights of Indigenous peoples to Free, Prior and Informed Consent

in the collection of data and their rights to develop data policies and protocols for data governance in their community.

A2: Data for governance emphasises that Indigenous peoples have a right to data relevant to them in order to drive internal governance decisions and empower self-determination and self-governance.

A3: Governance of data supports the rights of Indigenous peoples to steward their data based on Indigenous frameworks for how data should be curated, labelled, accessed and (re)used.

Responsibility asks that actors working with Indigenous communities and data contribute to expand capacity for Indigenous data governance through advocacy, training or other initiatives (sub-principle *R2. For expanding capability and capacity*) while endeavouring to manage and label the data in accordance with linguistic and conceptual frameworks of Indigenous communities to protect Indigenous heritage (sub-principle *R3. For Indigenous languages and worldviews*). Researchers and institutions have a responsibility to achieve these through building and maintaining positive and trusting relationships with Indigenous Communities during and after the research cycle (sub-principle *R1. For positive relationships*).

Ethics asks that the research and the data consider potential risks and harms to Indigenous communities and as much as possible address historical injustices while contributing to sustainability of data and its value. This means building data resources that do not contribute to the stigmatisation of Indigenous people and assessing benefits and harms from the perspective of Indigenous peoples (*E1. For minimizing harm and maximizing benefit*), addressing historical and current economic and social injustices through the research and data use (*E2. For Justice*), and considering the potential future benefits and harms that the data may cause. To address this, metadata grounded in Indigenous frameworks should clearly indicate provenance, purpose, and any limitations that can apply to data reuse (*E3. For future use*).

The CARE Principles are complementary with the FAIR Principles and not a replacement for them [6]. While the FAIR Principles [63] ensure that data is technically well-managed for discovery and reuse, the CARE Principles support alignment with interests and rights of Indigenous peoples. They do so by taking a people- and purpose-focused perspective on data governance that is consonant with relational methods prominent in Indigenous research [7], [8], [9].

One difference between conventional and relational methods can be gleaned from interviewing methods [8]. Interview protocols described in Research Methods sections or data management plans that we come across follow a clear structure and assume that the interviewee has a unique knowledge that, even as it is combined with that of

others at the analysis stage, is to be elicited individually. Deviations from the interview format, especially in fieldwork contexts, are not considered good data. From a relational perspective, starting elicitation and questions with one individual does not exclude the contribution of others if the context or interviewee themselves feels more comfortable in that way. Indeed, interviewees can ask others to join an interview and provide a shared perspective to the researcher. This is also considered valid and good data if it reflects the communicative codes that are most naturally practiced in the community in question.

By anchoring data strategies on the CARE Principles, researchers can accurately represent and share the data collected in accordance with both cultural codes and technical best practices. In the example of the interview method above, one way of implementing CARE would be to collaboratively develop data documentation that can capture different levels of interactivity and engagement during any interview session.

The CARE Principles also address risks that emerge from the use of Big Data in science and policy and adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI). Over-representation of Indigenous peoples in disadvantaged categories, e.g., incarceration data, risks perpetuating algorithmic bias in vital domains, including healthcare and the judicial system. In addition, research based on LLM models fed with these data is highly likely to produce biased and incomplete results [10], [11]. Developing data governance that is shaped by Indigenous knowledges while also addressing data needs of Indigenous communities mitigates these risks and brings the economic

and innovation benefits that Big Data and AI promise closer to community interests.

The CARE Principles can bring value beyond Indigenous contexts, where CARE-informed data governance can foreground the agency of other vulnerable groups on how their data is used or kept safe. While there are rich conversations and ongoing attention and outputs for research data management, FAIR principles, and more recently, compliance and security, there seems to be a dearth of frameworks² that specifically aim at enhancing the ability of a research community, especially historically marginalised ones, to make decisions about how the research and the data collected impacts them [12].

The authors of CARE caution against the dilution and co-opting of CARE either as a buzzword included in public-facing messaging without organisational implementation, or as a cookie-cutter framework that can be applied to non-Indigenous communities without further reflection or contextual relevance [2]. At the same time, they recognize that other collectives may benefit from the CARE Principles. Some such communities may include refugees and displaced groups, patient organisations, ecological rights and environmental justice groups, self-organised professional communities, consumer groups, LBGTQ+ groups, etc.

Implementing CARE-informed data governance in these scenarios will depend on community internal dynamics, the relationship with the government or other powerful stakeholders, digital readiness, and capabilities on both the community and the RPO side.

The CARE Principles and the Ethics Review Process in Dutch Universities

The Dutch Institutional Review Boards (IRBs) work with an ethics review process that is grounded in bioethics [13], [14].

This framework does not support the timelines and processes of participatory (fieldwork) research with communities. A key impediment is that the ethics approval process starts and concludes before the start of data collection [15], [16], [17], which in practical terms, in many cases means before contact is made with the research community. RPOs, funders and journals encourage researchers to follow their institutional ethics approval processes. There is currently no space to move away from the 'one review moment' model to allow community input throughout the research.

Even within the 'one review moment' model, Dutch IRBs do not practice collaborative review with communities where the research is taking place. Implementing CARE or CARE-informed data governance practices then becomes even more difficult because the data needs and

2 Existing ethical data frameworks are high-level and geared towards public sector and governmental institutions data initiatives (e.g., [DEDA](#) from Utrecht's School of Data Science, [Tada](#) from the Amsterdam Economic Board, the UK government's [Data Ethics Framework](#)) as well as international frameworks like [OECD's Good Practice Principles for Data Ethics in the Public Sector](#).

governance choices that communities make can only be determined in conversation with the community and through elaboration of research goals and benefits.

In recent efforts, the Dutch National Ethics Council for Social and Behavioral Sciences (NETHICS) has developed a Code of Conduct [18] that aims to address disciplinary and methodological diversity within SSH research, including ethnography and studies that involve co-creation elements with participants and communities. The NETHICS Code identifies **benefits for both research participants and communities** as relevant elements that are considered during the review and indicates that consent should be obtained in a manner comprehensible to the participant, taking into account cultural factors that may influence the elements of voluntarily participating in a research study. This is resonant with obligation of Free, Prior and Informed Consent (FIPC) applicable to Indigenous communities.

However, the Code does not contain an ethical obligation to enable benefits for the community through data specifically. In addition, the consent and ethics review is still framed as a closed procedure between the researcher and the committee where research participants and the community have only the agency to agree but not to co-create. On data management, the NETHICS Code includes only ethical obligations related to privacy law requirements and avoidance of harms through

re-identification of individual participants. The NETHICS Code does not include an ethical obligation to follow Indigenous or community-led governance choices in how the data is labelled and interpreted, where it is stored, how it is (re)used and how the data itself can serve the community needs.

The CARE Principles and Data Management in Dutch Universities

Implementing the CARE Principles in the RDM Cycle would entail alignment of RPO institutional policies, processes, data infrastructures and researcher practices with principles that uphold Indigenous rights in terms of data sovereignty and community benefit [19].

A key resource in considering the implications of adopting the CARE Principles is the CARE Data Maturity Model [70]. While the model is still in development, below is a summary of draft CARE Indicators that can guide institutional conversations³.

We outline initial implications for RPOs and relevant RDM community stakeholders based on this model as well as the input of our workshop participants.

3 The most up-to-date information on the CARE Maturity model can be found with the Collaboratory for Indigenous Data Governance: <https://indigenoustatalab.org/care-data-maturity-model/>. Readers are encouraged to check for detailed information.

Overview of Draft CARE Indicators (in development)

COLLECTIVE BENEFIT	AUTHORITY TO CONTROL	RESPONSIBILITY	ETHICS
Conduct data needs assessment	Recognition of Indigenous data sovereignty	Build relationships with Indigenous Peoples	Support use of Indigenous ethical frameworks
Utilise Indigenous identifiers	Recognition of Indigenous Peoples' rights to FPIC	Support community capacity-building	Promote Indigenous interpretation and presentation of findings
Supporting Indigenous use	Transparent ethics approval processes	Promote equitable attribution including acknowledgment and authorship	Share data of interest with Indigenous organizations
Alignment of permissions for data access and re/use to Indigenous frameworks	Transparent community permissions processes	Collect data relevant to Indigenous languages and worldviews	Reflect Indigenous knowledge systems in agreements
Indigenous approval of outputs from research projects	Enable audit of Indigenous data	Ensure data of interest are findable by communities	Compensate research participation
Ensure Indigenous Peoples determine benefits	Make disclosures to Indigenous communities about Indigenous data	Enable Indigenous metadata fields	Share copyright
Develop benefit sharing plans			Agreements reflect Indigenous methods for dispute resolution
Fund training and education			Administrative mechanisms for rights violations in research

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1. Integration in RPO Strategies and Policies

RPOs can demonstrate commitment to Indigenous data sovereignty by explicitly referencing the CARE Principles alongside the FAIR Principles in their multi-annual strategies, especially in light of explicit ambitions for taking responsibility for the societal impact of research. This can be through direct engagement with communities or under the umbrellas of Open Science and Citizen Science initiatives [20], [21], [22], [23], [24]⁴. Integrating CARE at the strategic level would emphasise that Indigenous data sovereignty is a component of responsible research conduct. This commitment can also be reflected in referencing the CARE Principles in Research Data Management policies and guidelines and adopting changes in the practical tools and support services for research data management.

2. Changes in Data Management Plan Templates

Data management plan (DMP) templates can provide specific guidance and ask researchers working with Indigenous communities or other vulnerable collectives to address CARE-relevant questions, e.g.:

- To indicate anticipated collective benefit for the research data, either through a data needs assessment, or based on prior research and conversations with the community and how they plan to share/create this benefit through the data.
- To indicate how they plan to allow for governance and access protocols that respect rights and frameworks of the community. This could be by developing data sharing agreements or other governance instruments, through adopting

⁴ I would like to thank Rene Bekkers (VU) for suggesting this point during the Open Science Festival 2025 session "Lessons from the CARE Principles"

relevant licenses (e.g., Kaitiakitanga Māori Data Sovereignty Licences [71]) or labels developed by those communities (e.g., Local Contexts metadata labels [27]).

- To indicate how they plan to select the outputs to be published while respecting the (legal) agreements made with communities.
- To indicate how they plan to acknowledge community contributions through acknowledgement, attribution, or authorship [31].
- To indicate how they plan to ensure that the data collected will be correctly interpreted in the future in relation to the cultural and normative context of the community.

3. Addressing Legal Hurdles

The operationalisation of CARE Principles and CARE-informed data governance implies governance of data based on trust and value-based relationships that are also reflected in concrete agreements. In such agreements, communities can lay out criteria for their engagement with the research, elements of data governance, processes for community consent, representation and acknowledgement of contributions and other relevant points on which researchers and communities can align.

Key gaps identified during the workshop with early-career researchers are the lack of awareness and clarity about the different types of legal agreements with communities and the resulting responsibilities for themselves, their supervisors or the institution as a whole. In addition, there is a lack of clarity on the legal status of individual consent, which is required under the GDPR for the processing of personal sensitive data, compared to community consent.

An LCRDM report on data sovereignty and data governance in research [25] clarifies that the responsibility and liability in case of non-compliance for data governance falls to the institution, and not on the individual researcher. From this perspective, the operationalisation of Authority to Control in terms of legal agreements would need institutional alignment. Some elements that Legal Councils in Dutch RPOs may choose to consider include:

- Developing models for community-level agreements on data processing or data sharing that recognise Indigenous data governance or CARE-informed data governance. These could be Data Sharing Agreements, Research Agreements, or Memorandum of Understanding types of contracts [64]. For more detail, see section 'Implementing Authority to Control' below.
- Clarify for researchers the legal implication of community-level consent and agreements in relation to existing legislation governing research data, including in relation to individual consent, IP rights, etc.
- Investigate how IP legislation and university policies can support the Intellectual Property rights of Indigenous peoples or, if applicable, of other types of communities and include relevant provisions in model contracts [26] [4].

4. Data Repositories

The Netherlands has an active and future-oriented ecosystem of data infrastructure for research data and high levels of expertise in the domain. The section 'Implementing Authority to Control' below addresses custom terms for data access, which various Dutch repositories already allow and which

provide flexibility for community-based data governance. Other suggestions from participants of our workshops include:

- Registering with Local Contexts [27], a non-profit organisation and digital platform that provides Indigenous-led frameworks for culturally appropriate data governance and metadata. This would allow repositories and institutions containing Indigenous collections to apply additional metadata to their existing collections and signal their openness to collaboration with Indigenous groups.
- DataverseNL can enable the Local Context Notices as these have been integrated in the main Dataverse platform as part of an Indigenous metadata block based on the Indigenous Metadata Bundle⁵. This would allow both DANS Data Stations and RPOs hosting their own Dataverse repositories to offer this metadata option for researchers uploading data.
- Archives, Repositories and Museums can enhance metadata and include multilingual translations and additions in the metadata based on culturally-specific information in collaboration with individual communities. [74]

5 I would like to thank Maui Hudson for this update.

Guidance for researchers

In this section we provide guidance questions for researchers who want to reflect on or apply CARE and CARE-informed data governance in their own research, taking into account the current ecosystem of ethics and data management in Dutch RPOs.

Implementing Collective Benefit

- **How do I articulate what collective benefit(s) my project will deliver?**

Arriving at a collective benefit is a collaborative exercise with your research community. In order to define collective benefit collaboratively, the following best practices can be helpful:

Begin conversations with the community as early as possible in the research design

by investigating whether there are any community data needs that you can meet through the research project. This can be either directly aligned with your research questions or you can explore secondary uses of your data even if an immediate and direct benefit is not easily defined. For instance,

if your research topic studies conservation efforts and focuses on a specific medicinal plant long used by a local community, you can begin conversations about how researching this particular plant and collecting data about it in a culturally-informed manner can provide or enhance not only health benefits, but also economic and social benefits for the community [28].

Endeavour to centre the community and its environment as a whole:

It is important to acknowledge that a broader 'community' is unlikely to be homogenous in perspectives, experiences, knowledge, and power. In addition, a community may include non-human entities, e.g., animals, plants, or rivers, that might be impacted by the research⁶ [29], [30]. Documenting the processes of community conversations and entities involved helps ensure that there are no significant gaps in representation.

⁶ For example, some rivers have been granted legal personhood in countries such as Aotearoa New Zealand and India, and consequently have designated guardians to represent their best interests - although the question of enforceability and what rights precisely are protected in the law for these rivers is an ongoing debate. See [30].

- **How can I incorporate collective benefit into my ethics application?**

State clearly in the application that you intend to work with a CARE or CARE-informed data governance framework

which assumes that data governance, risks and benefits from your data and research will be discussed and agreed to with the local community and that the ethics review application will detail that process.

If you have not had prior contact with the local community, explain in the application how you intend to arrive at agreements on collective benefit in terms of community engagement strategies. If you have already contacted the community and/or are a member yourself, clearly indicate that the approaches and reflection you've outlined in the application are already informed by contact with the participants. Reflection in the ethics review process of what you have already prepared for and worked on in the lead up to the application submission can provide helpful insight into the research project for the reviewers.

Please be aware that for each discipline, and each IRB, there may be different approaches to establish whether contact with a participant or a broader community is already the beginning of data collection or not. If you are in doubt about this, reach out to your ethics committee as soon as possible.

Incorporate collective benefit in your research methodology. This can involve indicating whether you intend to understand and address data needs, identify current community expertise and infrastructures before

data collection, co-develop strategies for data collection that are compatible with social and cultural norms, or options for community review of research methods and outputs. Methodological integration can also include fieldwork protocols that strive for balanced data collection across more and less influential stakeholders. This is especially beneficial in communities with no clear internal governance or clearly observable power imbalances.

Implementing Authority to Control

- **Are there laws and regulations that govern my work with the Indigenous communities or the collective I am working with?**

There are a number of legal and governance frameworks that govern how researchers engage with Indigenous rights to their data and knowledges. You can seek information on these through publicly available legislation and regulations. For example, the OCAP® Principles [31] developed by the First Nations Information Governance Centre in Canada give guidance on principles and practices supporting Indigenous data sovereignty. Researchers working with First Nations in Canada will be expected to implement these principles.

Similarly, many countries around the world have enacted legislation to implement the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples [32], which requires that Free, Prior and Informed Consent (FPIC) must be given by the community before any

activities (including research) within those communities begin [33], [34], and that benefit-sharing plans are developed. Another example of legislation that protects local knowledges is the Bioprospecting, Access, and Benefit-Sharing Regulations in South Africa [65], an implementation of the Nagoya Protocol [72] that provides the legal framework for obligations towards local communities for multiple stakeholders.

- **Can I sign a legal agreement with an Indigenous community or another collective if I want to work with CARE for my project?**

Whether your research is CARE-related or not, **you cannot enter into individual legal agreements with third parties** related to your research when employed by a Dutch RPO. You will need to have a contract in place whenever there is a transfer of funds to the community as project partners or beneficiaries, but other kinds of agreements do not necessarily need transfer of funds. In either case, because the responsibility for the data and research outputs in relation to third parties lies with your university, the signatory of any agreement must be someone that is allowed to represent the university legally.

Indigenous or other local communities may already work with model contracts.

These agreements generally cover issues of IP rights, data management, and publication. Developing this type of agreement as part of a research relationship is possible but will require discussion, and crucially support from your institution. You can seek the advice of your faculty's legal advisor on whether the

model contract or agreement proposed by the community fits with the existing practices and how to best respect the community terms. Alternatively, you can initiate the process to develop a research agreement. In cases where the community does not work with existing model contracts, institutional support becomes essential. If there is support, you can initiate developing an agreement or Memorandum of Understanding that outlines data governance roles, responsibilities, activities as well as commitments in terms of benefit sharing and other elements of CARE and CARE-informed data governance practices.

Agreements can be of different types of levels of specificity and enforceability [35]:

- A *Memorandum of Understanding* (MoU) is a non-binding agreement that can be drawn up between the University and a community representative that establishes good faith and mutual trust, and can include principles and ways of collaboration, mutually agreed topics of research, agreements on how the community will be consulted, etc.
- A *Research Agreement* is a binding contract between the University and an individual researcher that is a member of the community that is more specific and can include provisions on academic freedom and research integrity, decision-making processes and roles around data and community review of research outputs (i.e., data governance), and provisions on IP and publication rights.
- A *Data (or Information) Sharing Agreement* can be used when community data already exists, is governed either by the community or by an external agency, and must be

shared for the purposes of research. These agreements pay special attention to how personal information is managed to comply with privacy regulations, they include provisions on data storage, retention, permissible use, and can be based on refer to a data management plan.

- *A Joint Controllership Agreement* is a contract for GDPR compliance in collaborative research projects for the processing and protection of personal data and outlines the responsibilities of the party with regards to protection of the personal data. It can refer to a separate data management plan and is only related to data and research outputs.

In comparison with research agreements it is narrower in scope and does not cover other areas of collaboration with the community beyond the data and outputs.

- **Can I still implement elements of Authority to Control even if legal agreements with a community are not feasible for my institution/for my timeline?**

You can also implement Authority to Control elements in your Data Management Plan.

While data management plans are not legal documents and can be somewhat technical, they provide an excellent space for documenting in quite some detail processes and responsibilities for data governance in relation to all parties involved, including communities. Crucial elements of data governance can in fact be implemented through consent and data permissions, as well as labelling and metadata elements.

What is more, Dutch RPOs and funders consider DMPs as living documents. This allows you to document changes that may emerge during the research, including types of data to be collected, data access, additional metadata and labels applied to datasets or changes to the publication or archival strategy of research outputs after consultation with the community.

An important factor here is creating transparency for Indigenous communities and future users about the cultural relationships and responsibilities associated with the data. For example, you can indicate in the data management plan that you plan to incorporate Indigenous frameworks in describing the data, to ensure that the interpretation of variables, provenance, context, access, and value of the data aligns with choices made by the community. In addition, you can indicate that long-term archiving options will be explored to ensure that valuable data for a community can be archived in a repository that is governed by the community or an organisation that can provide ongoing access to the community [36].

In the concluding stage in the research, the DMP can be updated with concrete descriptions of how the project ambitions related to data governance were implemented and whether any changes became necessary driven by the circumstances or community preferences.

When compiling this information we encourage you to check the Research Data Management Policy of your institution to make sure that there is no hard requirement to uniquely publish and archive the data in the institutional repository. To our knowledge, most universities

in the Netherlands support the choices of individual researchers when it comes to publication and archiving of their data as long as that is done in a Trustworthy Repository. An ERC-supported list of Trustworthy Repositories can be found in [37].

- **How do I develop a community consent process in addition to applying individual consent?**

Community permission processes and community consent do not override individual consent requirements needed for GDPR compliance [38]. Permission processes for Authority to Control can however be implemented on top of seeking individual consent through community engagement and consultations. If there is existing guidance from the community on how to ensure community consent, this would be the main point of reference.

When working with Indigenous nations like the First Nations of Canada or the Māori in Aotearoa-New Zealand, you will find existing data governance frameworks and instruments [39], [40], [41], [42] and available expertise that can guide your work.

As part of your preparation, you can strive to find existing frameworks, policies or research ethics protocols and ethics boards that can help you start outlining community-permission processes for access and sharing of the data in a transparent manner.

For example, the AIATSIS Code of ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research [43] identifies community engagement built on

trust as the foundation for the research. The Code states that consultations and meetings with the community should clarify the goals, participation, resources needed, and decision making within the project. The shared understanding from consultation activities should then be reflected in a written agreement. Similarly, for health research that involves data from the Sámi peoples in Norway, collective consent is obtained through the Sámi Ethical Expert Committee for Sámi Health Research (SEEC) via procedures determined by the Committee, which was mandated with this authority by the Norwegian Sámi Parliament [44].

In general, engagement and consultation activities can include:

- Approaching elders or individuals chosen by the community as knowledge holders or key decision makers
- Broad community meetings where elders or relevant community experts are also present
- Community meetings which outline the research and the data processes and permissions requested in non-scientific jargon and, if possible, using graphics and illustrations to assist understanding [38].

In Indigenous communities or other groups that are not recognised by the state in which they reside or which are disadvantaged in relation to the majority of the population, guidance may be lacking due to absence of resources. However, customary and normative codes and leadership will very likely be in place to help you, if you are not a member of that community, navigate a community permission process following similar principles and

methods that foster trust, communication and openness as described above. Documenting these processes and obtaining letters of approval from the community, or writing down research agreements that include provisions for how data is accessed, shared and reused consolidates Authority to Control elements even in the absence of institutionalised governance.

- **How can you implement Authority to Control in the current ecosystem of tools for data storage and publication in Dutch RPOs?**

If research agreements and transparent permission processes with communities are reached and documented, the question becomes how to implement them in practice.

Archives and Research Data Repositories available to researchers employed at Dutch RPOs allow adding users who can control access to the uploaded data and materials. Access controls can be based on the terms of a Creative Commons (CC) licence or they can be Custom Data Access and Reuse Terms that clarify under which conditions the data is made accessible and available for reuse and who is responsible for processing access requests.

Applying standard CC licenses is not a sufficient implementation of Authority to Control, especially if CC licenses themselves do not include Indigenous-led acknowledgement metadata. Custom Data Access and Reuse Terms can allow you and your research community to express access and reuse elements that are not included, including culturally specific labels, frameworks

to describe provenance, purpose limitations, reuse conditions, etc. In the Netherlands, a number of university repositories running on the Dataverse platform as well as the DANS Data Stations will allow for custom data access and reuse terms to be used [45], [46].

This can be facilitated if a Research Agreement is already in place with the community that clarifies their governance role and identifies community bodies or researchers that would be responsible for processing access requests. In addition, a Research Agreement may also indicate whether they would need to acquire additional skills as part of this role and enable the acquiring of those skills.

Implementing Responsibility

The CARE Principles are people and purpose-focused. From that perspective, Responsibility is distributed and applies to everyone involved in the data cycle: communities, researchers, their institutions, and other research partners. You may not be able to implement Responsibility in all aspects of data governance, some of which are included below. The expectation is that individual researchers will be able, through this guidance, to identify what is possible and suitable for their research and context.

- **What does 'developing positive relationships' with a community mean for my own research project?**

What positive relationships between researchers and a community could entail is context dependent, and explicit or contextual cues from that community are the best source

of information. This guide can only hope to point you towards a productive path of inquiry. In any case, the starting point are collaborations that are built on trust, openness and respect, as well as acknowledgement of the value of the community's worldviews for the quality and value of the research outcomes.

Some questions that you might reflect on include:

- What concrete actions can I take to build trust with the community I work with?
Am I communicating my goals clearly?
Am I opening the research to include the views of the community I am working with?
- How do the concepts and paradigms that I am relying on to inform my research questions and data collection relate to the worldviews of the community that I am working with? Is there a tension that needs to be resolved? [41]
- Am I describing the contribution of community members in the research as comprehensively as possible and including them as contributors or co-authors where relevant? [19]
- Can I sustain a long-term partnership with the community that I am working with, both in terms of positive relationships and in the value that my research and data brings?
- Does the partnership create an open and encouraging space for the community to step forward on their responsibilities?
- **How can I intentionally build capacity within the community I work with so that their current and future members can meaningfully participate in and benefit from the research as well as the data I am collecting?**

Capacity building in a community can take many forms, but in the context of CARE and CARE-informed practices, this can be interpreted as ensuring that the community can reap the benefits of their data through developing a "data workforce" [47] that can continue to maintain or enhance the value of the data collected. This can be by working within a citizen science framework and facilitating the development and testing of data conceptualisation, variables, or methods of collection, as well as building skills for data management and visualisation [48] through training, platform development, software development, etc.

- **What does it look like in practice to take responsibility to respect Indigenous or community languages and worldviews with regards to data?**

The way in which datasets and data components are constructed and described is part and parcel of the research design and has concrete consequences for the development of the research questions and methodology. These choices will also have consequences for how data will be stored and reused by the community or other, external experts and researchers. From the perspective of CARE, opening these elements to collaborative review and approval in line with community principles would be the first step in taking responsibility to respect Indigenous or other community languages and worldviews. Make sure to inform yourself in the community about the most appropriate processes for community review [49].

Where clear review and approval processes for a shared understanding of data elements or descriptions are challenging to crystallise,

researchers can enhance the contribution of community members by taking inspiration from techniques in multilingual semantic fieldwork or utilizing knowledge representation methods if judged suitable for the domain or community in question [50]. This could start already with identifying the correct ISO specification for the language(s) of the community and including the correct and linguistically appropriate endonym in the metadata.

Depending on your research domain, you can propose to community members to carry out acceptability judgement tasks, elicited production tasks or translation tasks for specific concepts or descriptions that could be applicable in describing the data or variables therein [51], keeping in mind that not all of these exercises may be applicable [52], [53]. Indeed, applying formal methods uncritically to define what counts as variable, entity, or relationship may alter or flatten the Indigenous or community knowledge you are attempting to capture [54], [55].

Responsibility applies also at the dataset publication stage. Not all metadata fields in commonly used standards are applicable to Indigenous datasets while others need to be applied in accordance to community wishes, appropriateness, and cultural fit. For example, if the precise geographic location of a particular indigenous community or their resources cannot be identified due to cultural sensitivity,

then apply the description of a more generic geographic location. Similar mismatches with metadata standards can be in terms of temporal description of datasets, place names, and landscape terminology, etc. [56], [57]. Utilising Local Context tags and descriptions for the dataset(s), whether these are applied as tags in the repository or as part of the contextual metadata, is a step that you can take in collaboration with your research community and repository managers, to bridge mismatches in dataset and metadata descriptions until such time that metadata elements are included in relevant standards and repositories. The guidebook on sharing field notes [73] provides more examples of relevant metadata and documentation to include in the final dataset.

Implementing Ethics

There is extensive literature on data ethics for Indigenous peoples and vulnerable groups, which we assume that SSH researchers working with such communities are familiar with (recent titles: [58], [59]). The CARE Principles relate to the ethics of Indigenous data governance in terms of harm minimisation and benefit maximisation, the potential of research and data to address imbalances in power and resources, and the potential future uses and future harm that the data can create based on considerations of indigenous ethical frameworks. These elements can be extended and applied to other communities or groups. Some questions that can help you explore the above dimensions of ethics based on CARE and CARE-informed practices include:

- **How do I identify layers of risk for data?**

The risks of collecting and sharing data in Indigenous or vulnerable communities relates to historical and systemic imbalances experienced by the community as well as specific risks that are likely to affect the community. Broad considerations include risks of appropriation and misrepresentation [60], stigmatisation, external framing, loss of data sovereignty and commercial exploitation, as well as re-traumatisation or community exposure to pressure and backlash [61]. The specific history and conversations with the community can help you and community members break down these or other considerations into relevant risks for the community they are working with.

- **How do I help maximise the benefit of my research data?**

In collaboration with community members and experts, align the data or purpose of your research with specific needs of the community you work with. For example, if it is a community that is located in a disaster-prone region, consider how the research data can help maintain accurate administrative or historical records that would help its continuity and resilience [62]. Consider whether the data itself, and not only the research findings, can be useful for policy and decision making; to restore past harms, such as genealogy research and family reunifications; to help efforts for language preservation and revitalization [66], etc. Invite conversations with the community about the value of the data based on data and community needs as discussed in other sections of this guide.

To conclude

Researchers who work with Indigenous communities or other vulnerable communities often lack guidance on how best to handle sensitive and ethical aspects of their data. It is in a process of learning-by-doing that the relationship between ethics of doing fieldwork, connecting to the communities, and collecting data develops. While in the end this can be a very rewarding experience, it can also be a cause for individual insecurity and inefficiency. This guidebook uses the CARE Principles as the basis for providing guidance to researchers in working with Indigenous communities. In addition, it highlights the value of proceeding in the spirit of these principles when one works with other types of vulnerable communities.

The first part of the guidebook addresses among other things the ethics review process in The Netherlands and suitable forms for expressing data governance and agreements between Indigenous communities or their representatives and the researcher's institution. This is a step towards shifting responsibilities from individual researchers to an organisational level and towards a more efficient and effective way of carrying out the actual research. Furthermore, while there are no ready-made solutions on offer, we trust that the extensive guidance in the second part of this guidebook supports researchers to proceed with more confidence.

Additional resources

Training materials from the three-part workshop

This guidebook is based on a three-part series of training workshops. The project team created detailed session plans for each workshop, as well as slide decks for the various presentations, and the plans for all of our group exercises. Even though the workshops were attended by, in total, 95 researchers and data professionals, it was not possible for everyone who was interested in the topics to attend these one-off in-person sessions.

So, having put considerable effort into creating these innovative training materials, the project team deemed that it was important to share them more widely, making them available for reuse by other trainers in the future. To draw your attention to these, and to invite you to reuse them under their CC-BY licence, we have provided links to them in Zenodo below:

Flohr, P., van den Berk, M., Roodhof, A., Verheijen, J., Bruil, M., Thorpe, D.E. (2025), 'Workshop - Sharing Field Notes'. Zenodo.

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15600311>

Lushaj, B., Gelens, T., Magraw, J.-Y., Mos, A., Baloum, R.-C., Hati Gitundu, (Beatrice) BH. (2025), 'Workshop on The Ethics of Sharing Fieldwork Data and the CARE Principles'. Zenodo.

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15629394>

Thorpe, D.E., van den Berk, M., Flohr, P., van der Meer, L., Hesam, A., Campbell, R., Oberheim, F. (2025), 'Workshop on Hard to Share Data in the Social Sciences and Humanities and using the Secure ANalysis Environment (SANE)'. Zenodo.

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